

Strategies to decouple cell micro-scale and macro-scale environments for designing multifunctional biomimetic tissues

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Abstract

The regulation of cellular behavior within a three-dimensional (3D) environment to execute a specific function remains a challenge in the field of tissue engineering. In native tissues, cells and matrices are arranged into 3D modular units, comprising biochemical and biophysical signals that orchestrate specific cellular activities. Modular tissue engineering aims to emulate this natural complexity through the utilization of functional building blocks with unique stimulation features. By adopting a modular approach and using well-designed biomaterials, cellular microenvironments can be effectively decoupled from their macro-scale surroundings, enabling the development of engineered tissues with enhanced multifunctionality and heterogeneity. We overview recent advancements in decoupling the cellular micro-scale niches from their macroenvironment and evaluate the implications of this strategy on cellular and tissue functionality.

Keywords: Microenvironment; Macroenvironment, Modular tissue engineering; Microgels; Microtissues

Introduction

Conventional tissue engineering strategies combine cells, growth factors, and biomaterials to develop three-dimensional (3D) scaffolds designed for the replacement of diseased or damaged tissues and organs.[1] While considerable progress has been made using conventional scaffold-based tissue engineering, achieving the physiological complexity observed in native tissues has remained a challenge. Over the past decade, the profound influence of the cell microenvironment on their function has become increasingly evident. Environmental factors, such as mechanical properties, can significantly impact cellular mechanosensing, while the incorporation of ligands can facilitate cell adhesion.[2] By establishing a system capable of recapitulating key aspects of the *in vivo* cellular environment *in vitro*, such as cell-cell and cell-matrix interactions, it becomes more feasible to regulate features like cell shape, behavior, proliferation, differentiation, and migration, which consequently results in *in vivo*-mimicking cellular morphology and physiology.[3, 4]

Cells within native tissues are surrounded by a dynamic and complex microenvironment that includes the extracellular matrix (ECM), neighboring cellular populations, and numerous soluble factors, such as growth factors and cytokines.[5, 6] Cells are regulated by physical forces and chemical signals originating from their niche, delivering multiple stimulatory factors. The intricate micro- and macroenvironments surrounding cells are pivotal in orchestrating a network of signaling pathways that influence cell attachment, proliferation, and differentiation.[3] The ECM constituents that provide local signals to cells include physical properties such as roughness, stiffness, surface patterning, and electrical conductivity, along with chemical compositions like the gradient concentration of growth factors, as well as structural properties. These signals are integrated by cells through molecular recognition and mechanical transduction, and finally converted into signaling cascades to activate specific cellular processes.[3, 7] For a long time, the ECM has only been recognized for its structural role, which provides stability and support for surrounding cells. Nowadays, it is well-established that the regulation of cell behavior is influenced by the composition and characteristics of the ECM.[3] This can be seen in tissue engineering as well. For example, a soft matrix that mimics brain tissue directs stem cells to

differentiate into brain cells, while a rigid matrix that mimics bone tissue induces differentiation into osteoblasts.[8-10].

In the past decade, there has been a great development in the designing of materials providing biophysical and biochemical signals. Hydrogels are particularly promising for applications in Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine (TERM) due to their similarity with native ECM, water content, and biocompatibility.[11, 12] However, bulk hydrogels possess a nanoporous structure that restricts the diffusion of essential molecules as well as the removal of waste and also hinders the invasion of cells and blood vessels within their network.[1, 13, 14] The homogeneity of most bulk hydrogels also limits the incorporation of different signaling cues to guide cell behavior.[1, 15] More importantly, multifunctionality, which is an important feature of native tissues, is not achievable in bulk hydrogels.

Modular tissue engineering has emerged to overcome the major limitations of macroscale constructs. In practice, modular tissue engineering focuses on the fabrication of modular tissue microunits with specific biophysical, biomechanical, and microarchitectural features. These microunits serve as building blocks to design biomimetic tissues using bottom-up assembly processes.[16, 17] More importantly, they facilitate the decoupling of micro- and macro-scale environments, granting multifunctionality to the developed structure, a key feature in native tissue recapitulation.[18] Independent control over both the micro- and macroenvironments of cells enables the tuning of each cellular niche to suit the specific requirements of the cellular cargo. This may involve directing cellular differentiation towards specific lineages, while simultaneously tailoring the macroenvironment to possess optimal mechanical features. Embedding cellular microenvironments within a macroenvironment is also important for protecting them from external factors, including mechanical stresses and the host's immune system, while simultaneously ensuring sufficient mass transport of essential factors for optimal cell viability.[18, 19]

Overall, the compartmentalization of cellular niches facilitates the fabrication of heterogeneous and multifunctional microenvironments within a single 3D macrostructure. This design results in recapitulating both the structural and functional complexities observed in native tissues.[20] To

achieve this, microunits can be combined with biomaterials, which are subsequently molded or combined using, for example, biofabrication methodologies, into the desired structures. Various techniques have been exploited for the creation of these microunits that separate the cell microenvironments from their surroundings. In this review paper, the techniques have been categorized into two main groups: (i) Biomaterial-based microenvironment decoupling: this approach utilizes natural and synthetic biomaterials as building blocks to fabricate microunits capable of carrying necessary cargoes, such as cells and molecular cues. These microstructures can be designed with distinct mechanical, structural, and biochemical features, allowing them to host different cell types and support the development of co-culture models within a single macro-construct.[21] (ii) Cell-based microenvironment decoupling: in this method, 3D cell microaggregates or microtissues serve as building blocks. Due to their intrinsic ECM, these microtissues possess unique microenvironments separated from their surroundings. This intrinsic property enables their integration with desired constructs from other sources, such as biomaterials and hydrogels, without compromising the characteristics of either component, enabling the development of structures tailored to replicate complex *in vivo* environments. [22-27]

In this review, we highlight emerging strategies for compartmentalizing cellular environments at the micro-scale, while elucidating the significance of decoupling them from the macroscale environment when designing innovative tissue engineering approaches. We briefly discuss the latest research regarding biomaterial- and cell-based approaches for fabricating cellular niches, emphasizing the important roles of microgels and microtissues, along with introducing new approaches and outlining our perspectives for the future.

1. Biomaterial-based microenvironments

There are extensive varieties of biologically derived (e.g., alginate, gelatin, hyaluronate, or collagen) or synthetic (e.g., poly (ethylene glycol)(PEG)-based) materials that can be used for constructing material-based microunits.[28-30] These microunits include micro-sized hydrogels, microcapsules, microsponges, and cell microcarriers. The hydrogel microunits, or microgels, are currently the most used microunits for biomaterial-based microenvironment decoupling.

Microgels are versatile tools for tissue engineering applications due to their remarkable biocompatibility, potential delivery of important cargoes including cells and bioactive factors, unique tunability, and injectability via minimally invasive procedures.[1, 14] Microgels hold key characteristics that make them an ideal platform for recapitulating the complex and hierarchical organization of native tissues.[14] They can serve as individual cell culture units or be assembled into larger, heterogeneous tissue-mimicking constructs.[21] More importantly, their incorporation within a macro-scale biomaterial enables the decoupling of micro- and macro-scale environments, thereby achieving multiscale behavior and modular properties.[2, 13] There are various fabrication techniques to produce microgels using diverse polymers and different crosslinking methods, including batch emulsions,[31] microfluidics,[32] lithography,[33] electrohydrodynamic (EHD) spraying,[34], mechanical fragmentation,[35] and micromolding.[36]

In a microgel-macrogel composite (MMC), identical or distinct microgels are embedded into a macro-scale hydrogel (macrogel), which can be molded or bioprinted into a desired shape followed by matrix crosslinking (Fig. 1A).[37] The macrogel matrix keeps microgels in place and can potentially dictate the mechanical properties of the composite through chemical or molecular interactions.[2] Simultaneously, the properties of individual microgels can be tuned to promote desired functions of embedded cells.[38] These mechanical and chemical properties can be modified by changing microgel concentration, using different fabrication approaches, selecting different crosslinkers, and adding specific bioactive molecules.[39] Microgels within the MMC system can exist either in a crosslinked state (crosslinked microunit) or serve as sacrificial elements that can be subsequently liquefied (liquid microunit) following the crosslinking of the macrogel, leading to the formation of a microporous structure.[35, 37] It is important to mention that the characteristics of the microunit can be modulated based on the state of the microenvironment, offering more versatility to the system. For example, in a liquefied state, viscosity can be altered, or in a crosslinked state, the stiffness of the microunits can be changed. Other properties such as porosity and degradability can also be modulated.

In an MMC system containing crosslinked microunits, cell-laden microgels are embedded within an injectable or printable macrogel to fabricate a single construct with distinct micro- and macroenvironments.[14] For example, polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEGDA) microgels

encapsulating mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) were produced using a microfluidic technique.[18] Then, microgels were mixed with an extrudable macrogel precursor to fabricate a composite bioink with distinct micro- and macroenvironments. In this platform, the modular nature of the system was shown by embedding the MSC-laden PEGDA microgels within a proangiogenic fibrin solution loaded with endothelial cells. After one week, the endothelial cells had arranged themselves into a CD31-positive prevascular network, which was observed to connect and surround the microgels.[18] Another study reported the development of a modular bioink mimicking the 3D micro- and macroenvironment of native nerve tissue.[40] In their design, the MMC bioink was formulated by blending PC12-laden gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA)/chitosan microgels, fabricated using a microfluidic chip, with a GelMA macrogel precursor solution carrying RSC96 Schwann cells. The proposed MMC approach created suitable microenvironments for improving neurite outgrowth and elongation when microgels were loaded with nerve growth factor. The GelMA macrogel shell offered a macroenvironment recapitulating the epineurium layer, facilitating Schwann cell proliferation and organization. Confocal microscopy showed the decoupling of cellular microenvironments from the scaffold macroenvironment, with Schwann cells homogeneously distributed throughout the macrogel while PC12 cells were attached to and proliferated on the surface of the microgels (Fig. 1B).[40]

GelMA has been extensively used in MMC systems at both micro- and macroscales. For example, a bioink was developed by integrating electrosprayed cell-laden GelMA microgels with a GelMA macrogel precursor solution, serving as a cement.[41] Rat bone marrow-derived MSCs (BMSC) encapsulated in GelMA microgels were mixed into the GelMA precursor solution, aiming to implement an *in situ* cranial repair strategy for different defects. The bioink showed a better outcome in repairing cranial defects compared to the blank and BMSC-unloaded groups.[41] Similarly, another study reported the design of a cell-laden microgel-based biphasic bioink (MB) that was composed of jammed GelMA microgels, produced by a microfluidic device, were integrated into a GelMA macrogel precursor solution.[42] The MB bioink showed high bioprinting capabilities for fabricating complex 3D structures, as well as excellent tunability of its mechanical properties. Human hepatocarcinoma cell line HepG2 were encapsulated within the microgels while human umbilical cord endothelial cells (HUVECs) were embedded in the macrogel

precursor. This setup facilitated cellular reorganization and vascularization, which resulted in improved hepatic functions (Fig. 1C).[42] MMC production was streamlined in another study in which the decoupling of the micro- and macroenvironment was obtained through a one-step process using a multichannel microfluidic device.[43] Microgel-laden fibers were fabricated by encapsulating GelMA microgels carrying MG63 cells in an alginate solution, which was ejected from the microfluidic device into a CaCl_2 bath, forming fibers upon ionic crosslinking. These fibers improved cell-cell and cell-ECM interactions, which resulted in enhanced osteogenic differentiation properties. Moreover, the authors also demonstrated the application of this technique in muscle tissue regeneration using C2C12 myoblast cells, which showed significantly higher myogenic differentiation compared to the conventionally bioprinted structures, both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. [43]

The MMC approach has also been used in developing tissue models for cancer-related studies. In one study, GelMA microgels containing macrophages were produced with different mechanical characteristics by changing GelMA concentration. Results demonstrated that the proliferation and polarization of macrophages through lipopolysaccharide (LPS) stimulation were influenced by the mechanical properties of the microgels. An optimal mechanical environment (GelMA at concentrations of 9% for the primary aqueous phase and 12% for the secondary aqueous phase) was identified for macrophage proliferation.[44] Then, these macrophage-laden microgels were embedded into a GelMA macrogel encapsulating different cell types, either fibroblasts or hepatocarcinoma cells, to evaluate the crosstalk between macrophages and their surrounding environment. In the macroenvironment containing fibroblasts, macrophages treated with LPS showed significant proliferation and migration out of their designated niches. In the macroenvironment carrying cancer cells, more macrophages presenting dendritic M1 phenotype were observed over time compared to those surrounded by fibroblasts. On the other hand, significant cancer cell death was found around the M1-activated macrophages, showing their anti-cancer activity. They concluded that not only proliferation, differentiation, and migration of macrophages were influenced by the type of surrounding cells as well as LPS-induced activation, but also that the fate of the surrounding cells was affected by the state of the macrophages.[44] Another study introduced a new microfluidic technology for the fabrication of

customized PEG-heparin microgels for the development of 3D vascularized prostate cancer *in vitro* models.[45] PEG-heparin microgels with a stiff matrix encapsulating human prostate cancer cells (PC3) were pre-cultured for 7 days and subsequently integrated into a PEG-heparin macrogel with a soft matrix, enriched with growth factors and adhesion ligands, where HUVECs and MSCs were being co-cultured. Results showed that capillary networks were formed after 5 days of culture.[45] This approach addressed some limitations that conventional 3D *in vitro* cancer models had, particularly regarding their homogeneity.

In MMC systems containing liquid microunits, sacrificial microgels are liquefied (for example gelatin through heating or alginate by treating with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)) following the crosslinking process of the macrostructure. The morphology, shape, and size of the microgels have a significant impact on defining the porosity of the MMC system and can be customized for specific tissue engineering applications.[46] Moreover, porosity and induced local channels impact cellular infiltration, mobility, as well as the diffusion of nutrients and waste products.[46] In a particular study, researchers fabricated a perfusable hydrogel utilizing embedded 3D bioprinting technology, enabling it to enhance the transfer of vital nutrients and oxygen essential for cell survival within the macrostructure.[47] To fabricate the perfused hydrogel construct, an alginate hydrogel filament was printed within a xanthan gum methacrylate (XG-MA) matrix containing L929 cells. After photocrosslinking, the sacrificial alginate channel was removed using EDTA. Comparison of these structures with the bulk controls revealed that cells within the perfused hydrogel constructs exhibited increasing viability over time.[47] In another study, MSC-laden gelatin microcubes were produced by pressing a physically crosslinked hydrogel sheet through a nylon mesh.[35] Then, GelMA macrogel discs were produced by incorporating the gelatin microcubes into a GelMA macrogel precursor solution, followed by a chemical crosslinking. The authors were able to fabricate microenvironments with distinct viscosities by using microcubes of different gelatin concentrations to study osteogenic and adipogenic differentiation of human BMSCs. Culturing the macrogel discs at 37 °C caused the gelatin microcubes to melt, resulting in the formation of liquid microenvironments inside the crosslinked macrogel GelMA discs. Researchers showed that higher viscosity microenvironments obtained from 15% w/v gelatin microcubes better promoted osteogenic differentiation of MSCs

compared to lower viscosity microenvironments obtained from 5% and 10% w/v gelatin microcubes.[35]

All these reports highlight the advantages of the MMC system over traditional tissue engineering strategies (Table 1). In an MMC, both the microgel and macrogel composing the system can be independently tuned to possess the desired characteristics without any cross-interference. The MMC approach allows for the engineering of intricate tissue constructs that more closely resemble *in vivo* environments, with decoupled and better protected pockets of cells — potentially positioned in desired configurations — inside of a macroenvironment that can be shaped as needed. This characteristic cannot be achieved with traditional approaches that simply encapsulate cells within hydrogels, as they do not offer the same level of cellular protection and control. One other important advantage of this system is its potential to reduce the amount of growth factors typically required in tissue engineering applications.[18] Traditional approaches involve incorporating a high payload of growth factors, peptides, or small molecules into tissue constructs to influence cell behavior. However, this can lead to adverse effects, such as tissue inflammation, vessel leakage, and even cancer formation.[18, 48] The modular system offers the ability to incorporate growth factors site-specifically, either in the micro- or macroenvironment, allowing for a substantial reduction in the overall amount of biomolecules needed.[18]

Table 1. Overview of biomaterial-based microenvironments and their host macroenvironment. MSCs: mesenchymal stem cells; PEGDA: polyethylene glycol diacrylate; GelMA: gelatin methacryloyl; BMSC: bone marrow derived MSCs; PC3: human prostate cancer cells; HUVECs: human umbilical cord endothelial cells.

Microenvironment		Macroenvironment		Outcome	Ref.
Cell type	Biomaterial	Cell type	Biomaterial		
Human BMSCs	PEGDA	HUVECs	Proangiogenic fibrin	Endothelial cells formed a prevascular network	[18]
PC12	GelMA/chitosan	RSC96 cells	GelMA	Neurite outgrowth and elongation	[40]
Rat BMSCs	GelMA	-	GelMA	Enhanced cranial defect repair	[41]

HepG2	GelMA	HUVECs	GelMA	Improved hepatic functions	[42]
MG63 cells	GelMA	-	Alginate	Enhanced osteogenic differentiation	[43]
C2C12 myoblast	GelMA	-	Alginate	Improved myogenic differentiation	[43]
Mouse Macrophages	GelMA	Fibroblasts	GelMA	Proliferation and migration of fibroblasts	[44]
Mouse Macrophages	GelMA	HepG2	GelMA	Macrophages showed anti-cancer activity	[44]
PC3	PEG-heparin	HUVECs and MSCs	PEG-heparin	Capillary networks were formed	[45]
Human BMSCs	Gelatin	-	GelMA	Gelatin with higher viscosity promoted osteogenic differentiation	[35]

However, biomaterial-based microenvironments can extend beyond the use of hydrogel microunits. Our research group works with other systems with the potential to be employed as biomaterial-based microunits. For instance, liquid microcapsules could be easily integrated into hydrogels or bioinks. Their isolated and independent microenvironments, which may contain microparticles acting as cell carriers, can be used for assembling distinct tissue segments. (Fig. 1D, i).[34] Meanwhile, their robust membranes have been extensively shown to shield their contents from outside forces and processes, meaning the microtissues are protected during bioprinting and culturing, as well as from host immune responses after construct implantation.[49-51] Moreover, the membranes of microcapsules facilitate the separation of cells inside from those outside, enabling indirect co-culturing of cells and the application of distinct sets of stimuli. In previous studies, microcapsules were designed as micro-niches featuring a bioactive outer membrane, aimed at enhancing the agglomeration and integration into surrounding tissue. For that, microcapsules encapsulating MC3T3-E1 cells and microparticles were cultured on top of a 2D cell bed created from co-culturing HUVECs and fibroblasts.[52] Due to the adherent properties of MC3T3-E1 cells and the liquid nature of the microcapsules, microparticles are typically introduced into this liquefied cell encapsulation system to provide

adhesion sites. After an overnight incubation period, HUVECs and fibroblasts began adhering to

Fig. 1. A) Development of microgel-macrogel composite (MMC). Identical or distinct microgels are combined with a macro-scale biomaterial, which can then be molded or bioprinted into desired forms, creating uncoupled microenvironments. Each color of microgel represents a different microenvironment. This approach enables the fabrication of heterogeneous microenvironments within an individual 3D macrostructure. B) Designing of a MMC bioink by combining PC12-laden gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA)/chitosan microgels with a GelMA macrogel encapsulating RSC96 Schwann cells. The 2D views of confocal fluorescent microscopy images of (i) PC12 cells stained with CellTracker Green, (ii) RSC96 cells stained with CellTracker Orange, (iii) and the merged image. Scale bar= 500 μm . (iv, v) The top view and 3D view of confocal fluorescent microscopy images of a single GelMA/chitosan microgel encapsulating PC12 cells (stained with CellTracker Green) in the GelMA macrogel carrying RSC96 cells. Reprinted with permission.[40] Copyright 2020, Elsevier. C) Human hepatocarcinoma cell line HepG2, marked with CellTracker red, was encapsulated within GelMA microgels while HUVECs, marked with CellTracker green, were embedded in the GelMA macrogel (on day 0.5 and day 3, Scale bars= 200 μm). Immunostaining of albumin in HepG2 cells and anti-von Willebrand factor (vWF) in HUVECs on day 6. Scale bars= 50 μm . Reprinted with permission.[42] Copyright 2021, John Wiley and Sons. D) Schematic illustration of different biomaterial-based microunits such as i) liquid microcapsules (containing cell carrier microparticles); ii) platelet lysate microparticles; iii) polycaprolactone microdiscs; and iv) platelet lysate microsponges.

the outer membranes of the microcapsules, creating distinct environments inside and outside the microcapsules. Encapsulated MC3T3-E1 cells and microparticles formed microaggregates on the inside, while outside, fibroblasts facilitated microcapsule agglomeration into macroaggregates and HUVECs formed vascularized networks around and between microcapsules.[52] Such a system has the potential to fill out large tissue defects and could introduce an extra layer of complexity and tunability. The same cell encapsulation system was utilized as an immunomodulatory platform for the screening of different polymers potentially applicable in scaffolds. To accomplish this, cell-laden capsules with distinct polymers in the outer layer of the membrane were cultured on 2D macrophage beds.[53] This indirect co-culture can act as a predictive method for determining how a host immune system might respond to an implanted material (in this case the various polymers constituting the capsule membrane) but also how paracrine signaling between encapsulated and host immune cells might function.[53] Inspired by such a system, microenvironments can be designed to encapsulate desirable cells, combined with a macro-scale biomaterial that hosts the immune cells. This approach enables better recapitulation of *in vivo*-environments that the implanted material will encounter.

Another effective strategy for creating independent microenvironments involves the utilization of microcarriers. Microcarriers can support their own distinct microenvironments by facilitating cell attachment and exposure to distinct mechanical stimuli compared to the overall macroenvironment. Various microcarriers have been developed that might have the potential to be used in designing microunits including platelet lysate microparticles (Fig. 1D, ii) and polycaprolactone microdiscs (Fig. 1D, iii). These micro-scaffolds possess mechanical properties and topographies that can enhance cell attachment and guide cell differentiation. Moreover, with the assistance of these microcarriers, cells can aggregate, fostering the development of complex microenvironments.[54, 55] Another example of potential microcarriers are platelet lysate methacryloyl microsponges (Fig. 1D, iv). Similarly to other microcarriers, these porous platforms not only provide sites for cell adhesion and proliferation throughout their structure but also demonstrate the ability of the cell-laden microsponges to self-organize into aggregates.[56] Microcarriers can be designed to release drugs or other biomolecules of interest (like growth factors) in a controllable manner, adding another potential layer of chemical stimuli to the microenvironment for cellular guidance. For example, poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) microcarriers were designed to release dexamethasone, ascorbic acid, and β -glycerophosphate in a controlled manner.[57] Employing these drug-release vehicles for osteogenic differentiation showed that they not only supported cell growth but also conferred a robust osteogenic commitment to MSCs.[57] Furthermore, there is the possibility of combining multiple of these microcarriers to achieve unique microenvironment properties and configurations. Biomaterial-based microenvironments have been limitedly explored and we expect numerous additional approaches to be investigated in the coming years, as they can offer great versatility in how to engineer more complex and intricate *in vivo*-mimicking tissues for various purposes.

2. Cell-based microenvironments

Cells cultured in the form of 3D microtissues form complex microenvironments, growing in conditions closer to what they experience in natural tissues. These microenvironments are created through cell interactions and ECM production instead of with biomaterials. Such microtissues can be incorporated into materials like hydrogels with their microenvironments

decoupled from outside factors and can be combined as modular units to form larger and more intricate macrotissues.

Both spheroids and organoids fit under the broader category of “microtissues” — 3D tissue engineering building blocks formed through the combination and confinement of cells and/or micromaterials.[17] In spheroids, cells grow in high cell densities, forming a spherical structure that leads to increased cell-cell and cell-ECM interactions in multiple directions. This, in turn, improves cell viability, proliferation, and differentiation, as well as ECM deposition and protein secretion.[22-26] When spheroids are incorporated into hydrogels or bioinks, they retain their internal ECM, as it is not destroyed or sieved away in the trypsinization process like in monolayer cultures.[58, 59] Organoids differ from spheroids mainly in that they renew, differentiate, and organize themselves into 3D structures that, structurally and functionally, resemble the organs they were isolated from.[60-62] For this section, we will focus on briefly reviewing strategies that employ these microtissues inside hydrogels or bioinks for cell-based micro- and macroenvironment decoupling.

Incorporating spheroids in hydrogels and bioinks allows for mimicking the desired biological microenvironment without compromising the functionality of the hydrogel/bioink. This approach enables the creation of distinct micro- and macroenvironments to better simulate natural tissues. For instance, spheroids improved MSC survival in harsh, low-oxygen environments compared to dissociated cells or monolayers.[63] MSC spheroids and dissociated MSCs were both incorporated in fibrin hydrogels and cultured in hypoxic and serum-free conditions as models for bone tissue defect implantation.[63] The spheroids were formed through the hanging drop method. The study verified that spheroids better resisted apoptosis, secreted several times more vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) — indicating higher proangiogenic potential — and maintained their osteogenic potential, staying similarly responsive to osteogenic induction as dissociated and monolayered MSCs.[63]

Spheroids also serve effectively as tissue building blocks when combined with hydrogels or bioinks for bioprinting. They differ from the previously mentioned biomaterial-based microunits, where the microenvironment is produced with the involvement of biomaterials. Cell-based microunits create a microenvironment produced entirely by cells (each spheroid or set of cells is

an individual microenvironment), without dissociated cells or the need for a supporting biomaterial. In a study for articular cartilage lesion treatment, BMSC spheroids underwent chondrogenic differentiation, becoming cartilage spheroids after 14 days of culture.[64] In this work, spheroids were formed by culturing drops of cell suspension in non-adhesive microwells, with cells aggregating at the bottom of the wells. These spheroids exhibited a chondrogenic ECM, containing collagen II and glycosaminoglycans (GAGs).[64] When combined with a photocrosslinkable GelMA hydrogel, adjacent spheroids spontaneously fused and assembled into macro-tissues (as seen in Fig. 2A), forming cartilage constructs with the required shape fidelity.[64] Printed spheroid constructs showed higher cell viability compared to single cell ones due to the presence of cartilage-like ECMs before implantation.[64] Spheroids also offer cells more protection during bioprinting processes, shielding them from high shear stress, crosslinking radicals, and UV light.[58, 65, 66] Completing the trilineage examples, another study combined adipogenically induced adipose-derived MSC (ASC) spheroids in another GelMA bioink for 3D bioprinting of engineered adipose macro-tissues, in this case for breast reconstruction.[67] These macro-tissues were bioprinted, remaining highly viable in culture up to 14 days post-printing.[67] However, individual spheroids were restricted to sizes up to 200 μm — the oxygen diffusion limit *in vivo* for implanted tissues — as larger spheroids would experience hypoxia that is detrimental to differentiation processes without dedicated vascular networks.[67] This size is optimal for spheroid viability, and cell-laden biomaterial-based microenvironments, such as cell-laden microgels, share this optimal size for the same reason. However, it is important to note that the optimal size may vary depending on whether the cellular surrounding niche is solid or liquified, impacting the diffusion of essential nutrients and oxygen to the microenvironments. For instance, in the case of cells cultured within liquefied microcapsules, microenvironments as large as 700 μm demonstrated a high rate of viability.[50] Moreover, a liquefied environment, depending on the materials used in its construction, can maintain high viability even in macroscopic structures approaching 2 mm.[68]

Using larger spheroids and engineering bigger tissues through spheroid fusion require vascularization to guarantee the delivery of oxygen and nutrients to cells throughout the structure, allowing these engineered tissues to replicate the macroscopic structure of natural

tissues.[69] Microvascular networks resembling capillaries were developed using prevascularized spheroids printed in GelMA bioinks.[70, 71] These studies showcase another aspect of spheroids beneficial to tissue engineering, namely the ability for co-culture of different cell types within the same spheroid. In Moor et al.'s work particularly, ASCs were cultured into aggregates alongside fibroblasts and HUVECs, forming triculture spheroids. In these prevascularized spheroids, HUVECs self-organized into capillary-like networks.[70] Extrusion-printed constructs were implanted in chicken chorioallantoic membranes (CAM), successfully anastomosing with the embryo vasculature.[70] A more recent study further focused on vascularization, developing a granular-aggregate-prevascularized (GAP) bioink composed of prevascularized co-culture MSC/HUVEC spheroids as a discrete phase and a surrounding ECM-like solution comprised of GelMA and the biomaterial fibrinogen.[72] The spheroids composing most of this bioink granted printed constructs a high cell density and allowed the generation of deeply vascularized bone tissues.[72]

Conjugating spheroids (Fig. 2C, i) in bioinks or hydrogel matrices to separate their micro- and macroenvironments also allows for creating disease models. In one study, glioblastoma tumor-mimicking spheroids were incorporated in brain matrix-mimicking hyaluronic acid (HA) hydrogels.[73] This approach provided valuable insight into glioblastoma invasion, namely how a specific range of HA concentrations in brain tissue might be needed for glioblastoma cell migration to occur.[73] In another study, a cardiac disease model was developed by bioprinting spatially controlled densities of both cardiomyocyte and fibroblast spheroids in a purely supportive HA hydrogel.[22] Here, both spheroid types were formed using ultra-low adhesion well plates, with cardiomyocyte spheroids also undergoing centrifugation in the well plates for aggregate formation. Through this spatial organization and subsequently directed spheroid fusion, microtissues emulating post-myocardial infarction scarring were engineered. This included associated pathologies such as compromised contractility and irregular electrical activity, allowing for studying the effects of cardiac tissue regeneration-inducing microRNA treatments.[22]

Meanwhile, organoids (Fig. 2C, ii) are generally formed by seeding single stem cells isolated from a tissue or seeding multicellular structures — like cell aggregates (often formed similarly to

spheroids) and tissue fragments — into a 3D matrix. These 3D matrices can be natural ECMs, biologically derived matrices, or synthetic hydrogels, which mimic the natural microenvironment’s properties and drive their self-assembly through appropriate signals into organoids.[17, 60, 61] It can also be achieved through 3D printing, where organoids form from single cells assembled inside a printed hydrogel construct.[74]

Organoids have been embedded or formed inside hydrogels and other matrices for regenerative purposes or toxicity studies. Cholangiocyte organoids were incorporated into densified collagen hydrogels for repairing injuries in the biliary tree, namely the gallbladder and bile duct walls.[75, 76] As a therapeutic approach against hyperglycemia, pancreatic islets were embedded into an injectable, cellulose-based matrix, wherein they formed into a pancreas-like organoid capable of reshaping its microenvironment and producing insulin in response to glucose in type 1 diabetes mouse models (Fig. 2B).[77] Another study combined a HepaGR cell suspension with a gelatin solution to bioprint constructs wherein the cells formed gelatin-embedded liver organoids.[78] These organoid constructs were transplanted into mouse models with liver damage, where they matured and differentiated. They formed blood vessels connecting with the host vasculature and carried out liver-like functions 7 days post-differentiation.[78] In another study focusing on a drug-induced liver-injury model, cholangiocyte organoids were combined with a GelMA hydrogel to develop a bioink, which was printed into liver tissue constructs.[79] 7 days after bioprinting, these constructs were exposed to acetaminophen, a hepatotoxic compound, which led to organoid activity decreasing after 3 days of exposure. The shapes of the organoids became damaged due to cellular stress, showing the applicability of these organoid constructs as liver toxicity models.[79]

Table 2. Overview of cell-based microenvironments and their host macroenvironment. ASCs: adipose stem cells; MSCs: mesenchymal stem cells; HUVECs: human umbilical vein endothelial cells; GelMA: gelatin methacryloyl; HA: hyaluronic acid.

Microenvironment		Macroenvironment		
Cell/Tissue type	Microtissue type	Biomaterial	Outcome	Ref.

Human BMSCs	Spheroid	GelMA bioink	Spheroids assembled into cartilage macrotissues within the printed construct	[64]
Human ASCs	Spheroid	GelMA bioink	Enhanced adipogenic differentiation in spheroids in printed constructs	[67]
Human ASCs; Human foreskin fibroblasts; HUVECs	Spheroid	GelMA bioink	Printed constructs implanted in ovo and anastomised with the embryo vasculature	[70]
Human ASCs; HUVECs	Spheroid	GelMA and fibrinogen solution	Highly vascularized bone tissue constructs with high cell density, viability, and shape fidelity	[72]
Human glioblastoma cells	Spheroid	HA hydrogel	Glioblastoma disease model that displays the effect of HA concentration on glioblastoma cell migration	[73]
Human cardiomyocytes; Human cardiac fibroblasts	Spheroid	HA hydrogel	Post-myocardial infarction scarring model constructs for studying microRNA treatments	[22]
Human cholangiocytes	Organoid	Collagen hydrogel	Constructs implanted in mice, reconstructing biliary tree tissues	[75]
Mouse pancreatic islets	Organoid	Cellulose-based matrix	Constructs implanted in diabetic mice models, becoming vascularized; increased insulin and reduced blood glucose levels	[77]
HepaGR cells	Organoid	Gelatin solution	Constructs implanted in mice, vascularized with host; matured further hepatic functions, and alleviated liver failure	[78]

Although not as common as spheroids and organoids, other types of microtissues also have the potential to be used for cell-based microenvironment decoupling, such as cell sheets. Cell sheets (Fig. 2C, iii) are highly confluent cell monolayers that are detached from their culture surface

without resorting to enzymes such as trypsin.[80] As such, these sheets retain their cell adhesions and ECM, maintaining their microenvironments. Cell sheets can also include co-cultures of different cell types, diversifying their characteristics.[80]

This type of microtissue has already been incorporated into collagen hydrogels to create vascular networks and into other polymers to serve as transplantable, self-sustainable drug delivery devices.[81, 82] They have also been employed to create bioinks for scaffold-free 3D printing by breaking the sheets into smaller parts and aggregating those in the bioinks.[83] As such, cell sheets have the potential, like spheroids and organoids, to be used as cell-based microenvironments incorporated in and decoupled from a larger construct environment for macro-tissue engineering purposes. In one study, magnetic cell sheets with well-defined and controllable geometry, or cell stamps, were developed in a high-throughput method as customizable, patterned microtissues.[84] These cell stamps were intended for minimally invasive implantation and for use as disease models. The fabricated cell stamps were capable of invading methacryloyl laminarin (LAM) and platelet lysates (PLMA) hydrogels, demonstrating their ability of integration after implantation.[84] These cell stamps can also release trophic and immunomodulatory factors that, when combined with the properties of a surrounding macrogel or other biomaterial, can condition cell behavior. By incorporating them into such materials, either through their individual invasion or after assembling them into larger, controllable microtissue constructs, cell stamps have the potential to be used as decoupled cell-based microenvironments.

These studies showcase the ability of microtissues to establish their own microenvironments separately from the environment they grow in. Such decoupled microenvironments are shown to promote cell survival and development further than monolayered cultures, as well as being able to be combined to form more complex and *in vivo*-mimicking macro-tissues. They also offer more control over the characteristics of engineered tissue and allow for the decoupling of micro- and macroenvironments to achieve ideal conditions for each application. Combined with the potential for merging distinct microenvironments, these aspects make cell-based microenvironment decoupling a promising technique for tissue engineering. These approaches

Fig. 2. A) 3D bioprinting of 14-day-mature cartilage spheroids in photocrosslinkable gelMA hydrogel. Representation of (i) the CAD model and (ii–vi) macroscopic to microscopic representation of the printed scaffolds. Scale bars 500 μm (ii), 800 μm (iii), 500 μm (iv,v), 200 μm (vi). Fusion and cellular outgrowth of spheroids 4 days (vii) and 14 days (viii,ix) post printing within the gelMA. Black arrows indicate spheroid fusion. Scale bar 200 μm. Reprinted and adapted with permission.[64] Copyright 2020, Frontiers Media. B) Pancreatic islets seeded in the cellulose-based biomaterial, both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. (i) Aggregation of pancreatic islets seeded in biomaterial within 10 min *in vitro*. Empty biomaterial shows original small non-aggregated fine structures. Stereomicroscope imaging of resected islet-seeded biomaterial 5 weeks after initial intraperitoneal implantation into (ii) streptozocin (STZ)-induced and (iii) non-obese diabetic mice peritoneal cavity at 2.5x and 20x magnifications. Arrow indicates location of the aggregated islet-seeded biomaterial substructure nearest small intestines and

(original site of) pancreas. Reprinted and adapted with permission.[76] Copyright 2020, Springer Nature. C) . Examples of cell-based microunits include i) spheroids; ii) organoids; and iii) cell sheets.

improve upon more traditional tissue engineering strategies, which use single-cell suspensions embedded in hydrogels and other matrices.

3. Hybrid microenvironments

It is important to note that there is not always a clear line between cell-based and biomaterial-based strategies in the development of microunits. For example, there already exist cases where microparticles were combined with cells to facilitate spheroid and organoid formation, further complementing the microenvironment and enhancing cell survival, differentiation, and function.[85-88] Microcapsules have been used to encapsulate cells for spheroid and organoid formation, better protecting the formed microtissues under stressful culture conditions as well as controlling their sizes, making their formation processes easier and more standardized.[89, 90] Incorporating cells inside microgels for spheroid and organoid formation yields similar advantages, while also allowing for better control over the mechanical and chemical properties of the microenvironment. This offers the ability to better modulate microenvironments such as cancer niches or to focus on specific aspects of a microenvironment, such as studying cell signaling through the exchange of soluble mediators independently from cell-cell contacts.[91-93] More importantly, we expect the emergence of hybrid microenvironments in which both cell-based and material-based technologies can be combined to create heterogeneous microenvironments (Fig. 3). In an innovative work, microgels and spheroids were combined as distinct microunits in an injectable, granular composite.[94] In this system, MSC spheroids and HA microgels of similar size were mixed and placed into 3D printed molds before photocrosslinking of the microgels. The composites were then transferred to chondrogenic media and cultured for up to 56 days, where spheroids grew and fused into cartilage tissue, taking advantage of the mechanical stability provided by the microgels.[94] Such a combination possesses the advantages of both cell-based and biomaterial-based microunits, and could potentially be combined with macro-sized biomaterials for added benefits and further customizability. Incorporating hybrid microenvironments with their more intricate and

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of hybrid microenvironments. In this heterogeneous design, different approaches from cell-based and biomaterial-based techniques can be combined.

customizable properties into macro-scale hydrogels, bioinks, and other biomaterials will be the most complete approach towards recapitulating the complexity of *in vivo* tissues for applications like tissue engineering and disease models.

Conclusions and future perspectives

Over the past decades, modular tissue engineering offered a promising approach to address the critical shortage of replacement tissues for both research and therapeutic applications. Modular tissue engineering employs micro-scale building blocks with distinct biophysical, biomechanical, and microarchitectural features which can be combined with a macro-scale biomaterial to fabricate biomimetic tissues through assembly processes. This approach enables the decoupling of cellular microenvironments from their macroenvironment, allowing the independent design of each microenvironment to achieve the desired cellular function, while the macroenvironment can be tailored to possess ideal mechanical and rheological characteristics, as well as offering protection from mechanical stresses and host immune responses. The development of this field has led to engineering more complex and heterogeneous cellular microenvironments and recapitulating key structural and functional complexities found *in vivo*. However, there are still some challenges that need addressing. For example, it is quite difficult to keep uniform cell densities and drug loading within every microgel.[14] Moreover, spheroid and organoid production still face key obstacles to their application in clinical trials, like economic feasibility and time-consuming engineering of complex tissues. As such, production techniques are

continuously being improved, which in turn should lead to more robust and advanced studies and techniques on micro- and macroenvironment decoupling.

We envision that the future of TERM lies in advancing strategies that combine both biomaterial-based and cell-based approaches to decouple micro- and macroenvironments. By harnessing combined control over both aspects, engineered tissues can more accurately replicate *in vivo* conditions. Another main point of improvement might be in proposing more complex and customizable techniques for assembling and/or positioning microtissues in three dimensions.[95] These techniques would allow better manipulation of microtissue microenvironments or the patterning of larger, modular-based macroenvironments, subsequently improving macro-tissue engineering.[95] Similar approaches could be used for biomaterial-based and hybrid microenvironment positioning, allowing better control over the structure and functionalization of engineered constructs.

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